

MODERN CLINICAL AND LABORATORY INDICATORS OF TRANSIENT PNEUMONIA IN CHILDREN

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ABSTRACT

Acute pneumonia occupies one of the leading places among respiratory diseases in children, is characterized by high morbidity and complication rates. Especially in early childhood, the severe course of the disease, rapid development of respiratory failure and general intoxication symptoms remain an urgent problem in clinical practice. In recent years, certain changes have been observed in the clinical course and laboratory parameters of acute pneumonia, which increases the need for the use of modern diagnostic approaches. Therefore, an in-depth study of the clinical and laboratory characteristics of acute pneumonia in children is of great importance.

Introduction

Acute pneumonia occupies one of the leading places among respiratory diseases in children, is characterized by high morbidity and complication rates. Especially in early childhood, the severe course of the disease, rapid development of respiratory failure and general intoxication symptoms remain an urgent problem in clinical practice. In recent years, certain changes have been observed in the clinical course and laboratory parameters of acute pneumonia, which increases the need for the use of modern diagnostic approaches. Therefore, an in-depth study of the clinical and laboratory characteristics of acute pneumonia in children is of great importance.

Research objective

To identify modern clinical signs and laboratory parameters of acute pneumonia in children and assess their diagnostic significance.

Materials and methods

The study was conducted on the example of children diagnosed with acute pneumonia treated in the pediatric department. The clinical condition of the patients (elevated body temperature, cough, shortness of breath, signs of respiratory failure), physical examination results (percussion and auscultation data) were analyzed. Laboratory tests included a complete blood count, inflammatory markers (S-reactive protein), and biochemical parameters. If necessary, chest X-ray results were taken into account.

Results and discussion

According to the results of the analysis, the main clinical signs of acute pneumonia in children are a high body temperature, productive cough, shortness of breath, and symptoms

of general intoxication. Focal wet rales, muffled breath sounds were noted on auscultation. Laboratory tests showed leukocytosis, an increase in the proportion of neutrophils, and a high level of S-reactive protein, indicating the activity of the inflammatory process. In some cases, radiological changes are detected against the background of a mild course, which confirms the importance of instrumental examinations in early detection of this disease. The results obtained indicate the important role of modern clinical and laboratory indicators in increasing the effectiveness of early diagnosis and treatment of acute pneumonia.

Conclusions. Acute pneumonia in children manifests itself in various clinical and laboratory forms, and in early detection of the disease, a comprehensive assessment of modern laboratory and instrumental indicators, along with clinical signs, is important. This approach allows preventing complications and improving treatment outcomes.

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